

Enterprises of North and South Korea: A Pathway to the Peaceful Unification

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Abstract: North Korea claims that its economic system is perfectly normal and stable. The majority of the North Korean propaganda and media, such as “with our race,” claim that South Korean and other capitalist economies could not catch up with North Korean economic growth. However, based on the statistics provided by the World Bank and the U.N., it seems the South Korean economy is well above the economic development rate of North Korea. There have been constant observations that North Korean national economic income is significantly lower than any other Asian countries, due to several factors such as the unfair distribution of wealth, the dictatorship of Kim Jong-un, and even natural disasters. In order to effectively manage the North Korean economy and prepare for successful and efficient unification, there needs to be a constant comparison between these two states’ economies along with the establishment of joint enterprises.

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Question Prompt: Comparing North and South Korea’s economy; what are the advantages of each economy, and should there be a joint enterprise?; if investing in North Korea is allowed, which area would you invest in?; is there any country, company, or organization that were in a similar situation as North Korea that showed growth in the economy, and what is the possible way to do so?; what is the potential of North Korea’s economy in a free economy setting and what is the area with the most potential?

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North Korea claims that its economic system is perfectly normal and stable. The majority of the North Korean propaganda and media, such as “with our race” (우리민족끼리), claim that South Korean and other capitalist economies could not catch up with North Korean economic growth. However, based on the statistics provided by the World Bank and the U.N., it seems like the South Korean economy is well above the economic development rate of North Korea. There have been constant observations that North Korean national economic income is significantly lower than any other Asian countries, due to several factors such as the unfair distribution of wealth, the dictatorship of Kim Jong-un, and even natural disasters. In order to effectively manage the North Korean economy to prepare for successful and efficient unification, there needs to be a constant comparison between these two states’ economies along with the establishment of joint enterprises.

The South Korean economy rapidly developed after the Miracle of Han River in 1961 from developing countries. Before this economic miracle, the South Korean economy was still being focused on raw materials, similar to other developing countries, due to the aftermath of the Korean war and factories being destroyed. However, the government led by President Park began a New-village campaign, which rapidly increased the production rate of these major productions and political investment in new manufacturing industries. This enabled the South Korean economy to rapidly recover to a level where it could be a member of OECD. This constant economic growth and plans enabled South Korea to have

various international industries that produce the majority of the construction materials, automobiles, and electric devices, such as Hyundai and Samsung. The South Korean economy also became diversified to ship-manufacturing industries and tourism services as it also installed airports and other transportation to expand its business to services. Currently, the South Korean economy has improved significantly to a level where Korean companies are installing secondary factories in foreign countries, such as Southeast Asia. However, the South Korean economy on the production of raw materials couldn't be said to be successful since the majority of the raw materials manufacturing industries have either announced their bankruptcy or changed their main business areas to the new service areas. The South Korean economy also treats workers as important economic elements, which sometimes are used in various labor protests against their working environment or economic flaws, such as raising minimum wages.

On the other hand, the North Korean economy is currently still based on the raw material industries since it didn't have enough facilities or governmental support to expand and diversify its major economy. Instead, the government is only focusing on maintaining their authority, power, and economic wealth. For instance, while the majority of the North Korean teenagers are unable to go to public schools and receive a proper education, Kim's family even received education from Ivy League schools and other foreign schools which don't have a free education system. The North Korean government also invests the majority of its annual income strictly on the preference of the ruling family, including the

reform of the palace and invention of new weapons, including ICBM. As a result, the uneven distribution of wealth in North Korea is a serious issue that is currently an obstacle to North Korean economic growth. On the other hand, the North Korean economic system enables it to easily control the distribution of resources along with the life of citizens, since the government is the one who is responsible for passing the further legislations and deciding the next investments. This economic system has a decent advantage of the government being able to decide the next economic plan without any intervention or resistance from other political or labor organizations. Even if there are some workers who critically criticize the economic system, the government soon uses its secret police to arrest them and take them to rural areas, such as the Siberian plains, to force them to labor for the government away from their home.

As a result, while the South Korean economy has an advantage of rapidly recovering and expanding its major economic source of income, the North Korean economy has the advantage of being able to easily control the economic activities of citizens along with absolute power of the government to utilize the annual economic source. These two advantages could be united and used together using the joint enterprise system. This enterprise could be managed by both North Korean and South Korean economists and officials, which is similar to the Shared-communication center. However, this shared enterprise mainly aims to establish a stable economic system that has both the advantages of North and South Korea from constant debate and discussion between North Korea and

South Korean economists. These economists together propose various economic systems and generate the possible major advantages and disadvantages of each system or structure. These officials would also decide the most suitable economic system for unified Korea and predict the possible amount of money and other resources required for this system to be initiated. However, the challenge could be constantly seen, especially due to the ideological differences between the North and South Korean representatives. As North Korean citizens receive an education that justifies their current leader and dictatorial regime, some of the political officials could strongly disagree with establishing a close economic relationship with South Korea. Moreover, throughout constant meetings, these officials could also exchange their advanced technology or abundant amount of resources, which is one of the major successes in their current economic system. North Korean officials would receive manufacturing technologies that were developed from South Korea during the Miracle of Han River, while South Korean economists could receive abundant amounts of raw materials and other resources that could be found in South Korean regions.

It couldn't be denied that there are some considerable differences in the economy of North and South Korea along with their ideological differences. However, this joint enterprise would decrease the size of the gap between their relationships and become an effective method to prepare for the unification of the Korean Peninsula.

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